

Biogenetic-type Synthesis of Sesquichamaenol^{1†}

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A hypothetical biosynthetic pathway for the conversion of farnesylpyrophosphate into seaquichamaenol 1, a modified sesquiterpenoid isolated from *Chaemaecyparis formosensis* Matsum is proposed. The synthesis of 1 which lends experimental support to the proposed biosynthetic steps is reported.

The number of ways in which the enzyme bound isomeric farnesylpyrophosphate (FPP) precursors get folded and produce the incredibly large number of novel sesquiterpene skeletons has attracted the attention of organic chemists for the past few decades. The observed oxygenated patterns add further to the novelty and complexity of sesquiterpene skeletons thus providing rich source of interesting chemistry. The regular or normal sesquiterpenoids may undergo further transformations which lead to modified or irregular sesquiterpenoids and degraded or nor-sesquiterpenoids. Continuing our interest in the biogenesis and biomimetic synthesis of modified terpenoids, we report herein, biogenetic-type synthesis of sesquichamaenol (1).

Ando *et al.* isolated a novel phenolic sesquiterpene, sesquichamaenol from the essential oil of the Benihi tree, *Chaemaecyparis formosensis* Matsum (Cupressaceae) and assigned structure 1 on the basis of spectral analysis and a classical synthesis². These workers suggested that the biogenesis of 1 most likely involves C₁-C₁₀ bond fission of a cadinane skeleton 2. It is further proposed that 1 is biosynthesised by an oxidative cleavage of C₁-C₁₀ double bond of δ -cadinene (3) followed by aromatisation³. While there is no doubt that fission of C₁-C₁₀ bond of 2 takes place at some stage in the biosynthesis of 1, involvement of δ -cadinene (3) appears less likely and we considered an alternative biogenetic pathway for sesquichamaenol (1) as shown in Scheme 1^{4a}.

The cooccurrence of 1 and calamenene (4) in *Chaemaecyparis formosensis* together with the well-known acid-catalysed conversion of cumenehydroperoxide into phenol and acetone⁵ argue for the correctness of our hypothesis. Moreover, the biomimetic synthesis achieved during this

Scheme 1

study lends experimental support to biogenetic events proposed in Scheme 1. The key reaction for the C₁-C₁₀ bond fission is the acid-catalysed rearrangement of the hydroperoxide 5 (Scheme 1). The experimental procedure described by Kharasch *et al.*⁵ appeared ideal for this purpose. However, standardisation of the reaction conditions on a model compound seemed desirable (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Reagent and condition: (a) CH₃MgI, ether reflux, (b) AcOH, 30% H₂O₂ HClO₄ (cat. quantity), 1 h, room temp.

The tertiary alcohol 7, m.p. 78°, obtained from 7-methyl- α -tetralone 6 by Grignard reaction with CH₃MgI, upon treatment with a mixture of acetic acid, 30% hydrogen peroxide and catalytic quantity of 70% perchloric acid under stirring at room temp. (1 h) resulted in the formation of the expected phenolic ketone 8, m.p. 71°, in 70% yield. The reaction when performed on other model benzylic tertiary alcohols^{4a} afforded the expected products in excellent yields indicating the generality of experimental conditions.

Tertiary alcohol 13 required for *in situ* generation of hy-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

droperoxide **5** has been prepared before from 4-isopropyl-6-methyl- α -tetralone (**12**)⁶. We envisaged the preparation of **12** from 7-methyl- α -tetralone (**6**) as shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

Attempted preparation of tertiary alcohol **9** from **6** by reaction with isopropyl magnesium bromide led to the recovery of the starting material^{4a,b}. A new synthesis of **12** was therefore developed (Scheme 4). 3-Dimethylamino-*m*-methylpropiophenone hydrochloride (**14**), m.p. 160°, was prepared following the procedure developed by Nobels and Burkhalter⁷. Refluxing the heterogeneous mixture of **14** in aqueous KCN (3 h) gave the keto-nitrile **15**, C₁₀H₁₁ON, m.p. 58°. Hydrolysis of **15** with 10% KOH gave 4-oxo-*m*-tolylbutyric acid (**16**, R = H), m.p. 115°, in 55% yield. The keto-acid **16** (R = H) on reaction with isopropyl magnesium bromide gave the desired 5-*m*-tolyl-5-isopropyl- γ -butyrolactone (**17**), as a colourless oil having spectral prop-

erties identical with those of an authentic specimen⁶. Polyphosphoric acid cyclisation of 4-isopropyl-4-*m*-tolyl- γ -butyrolactone (**17**) according to the method of Mane and Rao⁸ gave a poor yield of tetralone **12**.

The desired tetralone **12** could be obtained in good yield by an alternative route. Methyl ester of 4-oxo-4-*m*-tolylbutyric acid, (**16**, R = CH₃) on reaction with isopropyl magnesium bromide gave the mixture of unsaturated methylesters **18** in 65% yield. Catalytic hydrogenation of **18** in ethanol in the presence of Pd-C (10%) furnished the saturated ester **19** which was cyclised by polyphosphoric acid in excellent yield to 4-isopropyl-7-methyl- α -tetralone (**12**) in 80% yield and having spectral properties identical to those reported in the literature⁶. Reaction of **12** with methyl magnesium iodide and ammonium chloride work-up gave a 60 : 40 mixture of α -calacorene (**20**), C₁₅H₂₀, and tertiary alcohol **13**. Treatment of **13** with a mixture of acetic acid, 30% hydrogen peroxide and catalytic quantity of 70% perchloric acid under stirring at room temp. (1 h) afforded pure sesquichamaenol (**1**), m.p. 110°, in 72% yield. It was found that *in situ* generation of hydroperoxide **5** is also possible from the mixture of α -calacorene (**20**) and tertiary alcohol **13**. The synthetic seaquichamaenol (**1**) was found to be identical in all respects (m.p., co-tlc, ir, nmr, ms) with natural sesquichamaenol.

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Sesquichamaenol has been synthesised before by other investigators^{10,11}, but the recent synthesis reported by Ho and Yang^{12,13}, deserves special mention as the key reaction involving C₁-C₁₀ bond cleavage is identical with our method and differs only in the experimental conditions. We believe that the biogenesis of structurally related phenolic ketone, himasecolone (**21**)¹⁴ also proceeds through the acid-catalysed rearrangement of a tertiary benzylic hydroperoxide precursor¹⁵. Our synthetic studies concerning himasecolone (**21**) and other structurally related phenolic ketones will be reported elsewhere.

In conclusion, two groups^{12,16} have independently proposed a identical hypothesis for the biogenetic origin of phenolic sesquiterpenoids **1** and **21** and substantiated the biogenetic proposal by synthesis of **1**. We are certain that the present biogenetic proposal will stand to the results of tracer studies, if carried out.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Scheme 4 Reagent and condition (a) aqueous KCN, Δ , (b) aqueous NaOH, Δ , (c) *i*-pn-MgBr, ether on **16** (R = H), (d) CH₃OH, H₂SO₄, Δ on **16** (R = H), *i*-pr-MgBr, ether CH₃OH, H₂SO₄, Δ , (e) Pd/C, EtOH, (f) PPA, (g) CH₃Mgl, ether

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-1100 spectrophotometer. Spectral data (^1H nmr and ms) were obtained through the courtesy of various institution; no details of individual instruments are therefore given. The chemical shifts in ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) are expressed in δ ppm with internal reference tetramethylsilane.

3-Dimethylamino-m-methylpropiophenone hydrochloride (**14**) : It was prepared following the literature procedure⁷, m.p. 160°.

3-Oxo-3-m-tolyl-1-cyanopropane (**15**) : To a mixture of **14** (28.7 g) and potassium cyanide (17.5 g) was added boiling water (340 ml). The heterogenous mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The solid separated on cooling was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from benzene : petroleum ether to give the keto-nitrile **15** (18.6 g, 80%), m.p. 58° (Found : C, 74.31; H, 6.93, N, 8.82. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}$ requires : C, 74.54; H, 6.83, N, 8.7%); ν_{max} 3100, 2320, 1688, 1612, 1600 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (60 MHz) 2.43 (3H, s), 2.63 (2H, m), 3.3 (2H, m), 7.23–7.87 (4H, m).

4-Oxo-4-m-tolylbutyric acid (**16**) : A mixture of **15** (18.0 g) and aqueous NaOH (10%; 30 ml) was stirred at reflux for 16 h. The resulting red solution was then cooled, poured over cold water (100 ml) and extracted with ether (2×75 ml). The aqueous portion was acidified with conc. HCl. The precipitated solid was filtered and purified by crystallisation from ethanol : water to give the keto-acid **16** (16.5 g, 82.6%), m.p. 115° (Found : C, 69.01; H, 6.01. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 68.76; H, 6.25%); ν_{max} 3330–2600, 1715, 1675, 1600 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (60 MHz) 2.43 (3H, s), 2.93 (2H, t), 3.53 (2H, t), 7.23–8.0 (4H, m).

4-Isopropyl-4-m-tolyl- γ -butyrolactone (**17**) : The keto-acid **16** (16.5 g) in dry ether (100 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 30 min to a solution of isopropyl magnesium bromide [prepared from magnesium (8.25 g) and isopropyl bromide (42.3 g)] in dry ether. During the addition, the temperature of the mixture was maintained at 0–5°. It was then brought to room temperature, then refluxed for 24 h, poured over crushed ice, acidified with concentrated HCl and stirred for 30 min. The ether layer was separated and aqueous phase was extracted with ether (2×50 ml). The combined organic phase was washed with NaHCO_3 solution, water and dried. Removal of ether gave a residue, which was purified by distillation under reduced pressure (10 mm) to afford **17** as colourless oil (10.73 g, 53.35%); ν_{max} 1770, 1595 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (60 MHz) 0.84 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 0.97 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 1.96–2.6 (5H, m), 2.34 (3H, s), 6.9–7.3 (4H, m). Direct comparison of the ir and ^1H nmr spectra with those recorded on authentic **17** established the identity.

PPA cyclisation of γ -lactone (17) to 4-isopropyl-6-methyl- α -tetralone (**12**) : γ -Lactone **17** (5.5 g) was subjected

to PPA cyclisation using the reported procedure⁸. Work-up in usual manner yielded pure **12** (0.5 g) having spectral data identical with those recorded on authentic sample⁶.

Attempted preparation of 3,4-dihydro-1-hydroxy-1-isopropyl-7-methylnaphthalene (**9**) : Grignard reaction of 7-methyl- α -tetralone **6** with isopropyl magnesium bromide in dry ether (24 h, reflux) followed by usual work-up resulted in the recovery of **6**.

Methyl-4-isopropyl-4-m-tolylbutyrate (**19**) from **17** : To zinc amalgam [prepared from zinc dust (1.44 g), HgCl_2 (0.144 g), concentrated HCl (0.1 ml) and water (1.8 ml)] was added **17** (0.6 g), water (0.9 ml), concentrated HCl (2.1 ml), toluene (10 ml), and the mixture was refluxed for 62 h. Concentrated HCl was added in four portions (0.6 ml each) at regular intervals during the course of refluxing period. On cooling, the reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was extracted with ether (3×20 ml). The combined ether extracts was washed thoroughly with dilute aqueous NaOH. The aqueous alkaline phase was neutralised with concentrated HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract after drying was concentrated to afford the acidic residue (0.255 g, 42%) which on Fischer esterification with methanol-conc. H_2SO_4 afforded **19** in almost quantitative yield (from acid). The ester **19** was also prepared from **16** as given below.

Conversion of 4-oxo-4-m-tolylbutyric acid (16) into 19 : A mixture of **16** (3.0 g), methanol (50 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (1.0 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Methanol was then removed by distillation, water (100 ml) added to the residue and extracted with ether. The ether extract after drying was concentrated and purified by distillation under reduced pressure to afford methyl-4-oxo-4-m-tolyl butyrate **16** ($R = \text{CH}_3$) as oil (2.41 g, 74.9%). The ester thus obtained was used as such in the next step.

Unsaturated ester mixture 18 from 16 ($R = \text{CH}_3$) : A solution of methyl-4-oxo-4-m-tolylbutyrate (2.4 g) in anhydrous ether (20 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of isopropyl magnesium bromide [prepared from magnesium (0.48 g), isopropyl bromide (2.5 ml)] in dry ether (50 ml) maintaining the reaction temperature at 0–5°. It was then allowed to reach room temperature and dry toluene (25 ml) was added. Ether was removed by distillation, then the reaction mixture heated at 100° for 6 h, allowed to cool and decomposed with saturated NH_4Cl solution. Toluene layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with ether (3×20 ml). The combined organic layers was washed with water, dried and concentrated to give a residue, which was then refluxed in methanol (35 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (6 ml) for 6 h. The usual work-up followed by filtration through a short silica gel column afforded **18** (1.64 g, 60.7%) as a mixture of two isomers (isopropylidene iso-

mer, 84%) : δ_{H} (60 MHz; CCl_4) 1.5 (3H, s), 1.8 (3H, s), 2.26 (3H, s), 3.63 (3H, s), 6.7–7.2 (4H, m).

Methyl-4-isopropyl-4-m-tolylbutyrate (19) : A mixture of the ester 18 (1.64 g) and 10% Pd-charcoal (0.17 g) was hydrogenated in ethanol (30 ml). When the absorption of hydrogen ceased, the catalyst was filtered off and ethanol was evaporated. Purification of the product by distillation under reduced pressure afforded 19 as a colourless oil (1.57 g, 95.3%) (Found : C, 76.81; H, 9.47. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 76.9; H, 9.4%); ν_{max} 1745, 1610, 1590, 1165, 1035, 780 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (90 MHz) 0.75 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 0.99 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 1.6–2.3 (5H, m), 2.34 (3H, s), 2.6 (1H, m), 3.55 (3H, s), 6.7–7.2 (4H, m).

4-Isopropyl-6-methyl- α -tetralone (12) : The ester 19 (1.57 g) was added to a slurry of PPA [prepared from P_2O_5 (9 g) and H_3PO_4 (5 ml)] and the mixture was stirred at 95° for 2 h. The mixture was poured over crushed ice, extracted with ether (3×20 ml). The combined ether extracts was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution and then with water. The organic phase after drying was concentrated to afford a residue which was purified by chromatography over silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave 12 (1.11 g, 85.5%) (Found : C, 83.07; H, 8.94. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires : C, 83.17; H 8.9%); ν_{max} 1680, 1605, 1281, 1234, 1130, 1030, 932, 874, 810 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (60 MHz; CCl_4) 0.93 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 0.95 (3H, d, J 7 Hz), 1.8–2.6 (6H, m), 2.32 (3H, s), 6.94 (1H, s), 6.98 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.78 (1H, d, J 8 Hz).

Conversion of 4-isopropyl-6-methyl- α -tetralone 12 into 13 and 20 : To a solution of 12 (0.9 g) in anhydrous ether (20 ml) was added dropwise under stirring methyl magnesium iodide [prepared from magnesium (0.213 g) and methyl iodide (1.26 g)] over a period of 30 min at 0°. The reaction mixture was brought to room temp. and left for 24 h under stirring, decomposed with ice-cold saturated solution of ammonium chloride and extracted with ether (3×25 ml). The combined ether layers after washing with water was dried and concentrated to give a residue (0.98 g) which was found to be a mixture of two components by tlc, the less polar hydrocarbon 20 and the tertiary alcohol 13. It was considered that *in situ* preparation of hydroperoxide precursor would be possible even from 20 and hence the mixture of 13 and 20 as such was used in the last step.

Conversion of tertiary alcohol 7 into 8 : The alcohol 7 (0.75 g) was added to a stirring mixture of acetic acid (32 ml), 30% hydrogen peroxide (4.3 ml) and 70% perchloric acid (1 ml) at room temp. and the stirring was continued for 1h. The mixture was then poured over crushed ice, extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate. The ether

layer was then extracted with 2N NaOH and the alkaline aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated HCl, extracted with benzene, dried and concentrated to give a solid residue, which was purified further by crystallisation, (0.563 g, ~70%), m.p. 71° (Found : C, 75.31; H, 8.20. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 75.1; H, 8.33%); ν_{max} 3600, 1710, 1625, 1570, 1525, 1330, 1300, 1215, 1110, 1100, 990, 940, 860, 818, 790 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (60 MHz) 2.2 (3H, s), 2.3 (3H, s), 1.5–2.03 (2H, m), 2.33–2.7 (4H, m) 6.5–7.0 (3H). The spectral and analytical data showed it to be 8.

Sesquichamaenol (1) *from the mixture of 13 and 20* : A mixture of 13 and 20 (0.98 g) was added to a stirring mixture of acetic acid (42 ml), 30% H_2O_2 (5.7 ml) and 70% perchloric acid (1.3 ml) at room temp. The work up was done as in the previous experiment to afford a yellow viscous liquid (0.63 g). It was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) gave a solid (0.3 g, 28.57%), which was further purified by crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1), m.p. 110°, and identified as 1 from the physical constants and spectral data : m/z 234 (M^+), 191, 163, 133, 121, 43; δ_{H} (90 MHz) 0.73 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.99 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 2.02 (3H, s), 2.23 (3H, s), 5.25 (1H, bs, exchangeable with D_2O), 6.55 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 6.79 (1H, s), 6.83 (1H, d, J 8 Hz). The synthetic 1 was identical in all respects with natural sesquichamaenol (m.m.p., co-tlc, ir, ^1H nmr, MS). When only tertiary alcohol 13 was used in place of the mixture of 13 and 20, sesquichamaenol 1 was obtained in 72% yield. (The fission products are obtained in high yields, when H_2O_2 used was from a freshly opened bottle).

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